

**CRIME INVESTIGATION, PRIVACY RIGHT & SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS IN
AFRICA: LESSONS FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION LAW**

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Abstract

As social media platform advanced and wide spread in the Africa, the crimes on the platform are expanded as well. One undermines the other's nations, cultures, ethnical origins, physical appearances, races, languages, etc. via social media platforms. On the other hand, the users deceive people in the media by sharing false appointment, false removal fabricated letter of political officials, insulting of political officials and terrorizing an individual or groups as resulting death or destructing its property and other activities. EU law and the legal regimes of Ethiopia, South Africa, and Tanzania offer different types of experiences and lessons. The EU has the most advanced data protection law, the General Data Protection Act (GDPR) OF 2016 and lex specialis on law enforcement while South Africa has implemented a modest data protection law, the Protection of Personal Information Act (POPI) of 2013. Tanzania has more or less good case laws to get evidence and information from the social media platforms, especially Facebook. While Ethiopia has unique political and legal context due to lack of comprehensive privacy law. No body can violate the privacy of rights of any persons unless prescribed by law, necessary and proportionate. It aims to examine the legal regime (or the lack of such regime) governing acquisition of evidence from social media platforms and the legal challenges including privacy and lack of institutional mechanisms to obtain evidence for domestic crime investigation. The research analysis the conflict between achieving criminal justice and protecting privacy rights of the suspects. It also aims to explore the institutional challenges African countries may/do face in attempting to obtain evidence from social media giants like Facebook. The ultimate goal of this research is to provide fertile ground for political, economic, and legal reform in Africa regarding the handling of personal data for criminal investigation and to shed a light on the challenges and opportunities related to using social media as investigative tool and how African countries could use their economic leverage and legal institutions to work with data controllers in crime investigation.

Keywords: Crime Investigation, Social Media platform, Privacy Rights Law, European Union Law.

1. Introduction

The emergence of big social media platforms has brought with itself many socio-economic challenges and opportunities. For criminal law, the primary challenge is to strike a balance between two conflicting goals. On the one hand, criminal law has to ensure that criminal investigation brings criminal offenders to justice using all the legal tools available. Social media platforms such as Facebook can be useful tools in obtaining incriminating information available publicly and hence provides a good investigative information. On the other hand, human rights, in particular, the right to privacy prevents the disclosure of information to investigative authorities. Although incriminating information about suspects may be deleted from public spaces, they are not necessarily automatically erased from the database of the platform concerned. But acquiring such information may not be possible due to privacy concerns as well as lack of legal regimes governing the acquisition of such evidence.

African countries have witnessed the prominence of social media over the past few years with old and young people becoming part of the technology. It has also been observed over the years that hints of criminal offenses have been given in advance of the commission of crimes. In many instances, evidences of criminal offences are often found on social media. But the role of such evidence and the legal means of acquiring it is both understudied and less understood in Africa.

Nevertheless, the political, economic, and legal framework in Africa does not provide effective tool for law enforcement to obtain evidence from social media platforms. Three factors can be considered key in explaining the challenge. First, African countries do not have comprehensive privacy, data protection laws that create a conducive environment in which law enforcement agencies can obtain evidence from data controllers such as Facebook. Second, even if there is the political will and legal means to achieve that, lack of strong economic leverage makes it nearly impossible to dictate the behaviors of social media giants. In other words, since the major revenue for Facebook comes from US, Europe and Asia, African countries have little leverage to compel Facebook to submit to court orders. The situation is aggravated by capital control which provides a *prima facie* evidence that Facebook's revenue does not depend on activities taking place in these countries. Third, unlike in the US or EU where Facebook has headquarters that can be subjected to the jurisdiction of courts and e sanctioned, African countries do not have personal jurisdiction on major social media platforms, with the exception of South Africa where Facebook has recently established a headquarters. The above three factors make crime investigation and access to data from social media platforms difficult in Africa.

The EU has privacy law that ensures that social media platforms and other data controllers provide access to data upon request by law enforcement agencies and courts. The EU besides having the most advanced data protection law in the world has a parallel legislation dealing with data protection and law enforcement name the Law Enforcement Directive. No study has been conducted on the legal regimes in Africa and the impact of the lack economic and institutional leverage of African countries on social media platforms.

2. CRIME INVESTIGATION ON SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS

Crime investigation may be conducted by an official of the crime investigation office, will utilize social media company to seek or retain information, it conducting criminal investigations, and solving reported crime; or based upon reasonable suspicion that an identifiable individual, or organization has committed an identifiable criminal offense or is involved in or is planning criminal conduct or activity that presents a threat to any individual, the community, or the nation and the information is relevant to the criminal conduct or activity; or is relevant to the investigation and prosecution of suspected criminal incidents. Today, social media is a fantastic method to interact with others and has supported in new forms of communication in our most society. It plays an important role in connecting individuals to communicate through social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, and YouTube. This communication includes tweeting, sharing photos and images, liking and commenting, and other forms of interaction. In the criminal justice system, social media can be used for community outreach events such as providing crime prevention ways, providing crime locations, and to ask information about unentertained crimes. Social media can also be used to make time accurate notifications regarding special events, weather the incidents, or missing or injured persons.¹ Investigation of social media crime is been evaluated and determined to be relevant to the identification of criminal activity engaged in by individuals, or organizations which, are reasonably suspected of involvement in criminal activity.

However, it is unfortunate that social networking sites can pose a number of major security issues,² dangers, and sorts of assaults. And it brings societal crisis by transmitting disinformation and hate speech.³

In nations like the United States, police enforcement can aggressively monitor such social media accounts because the information is public and there are no legal restrictions on seeing or monitoring such social media presence.⁴ Law enforcement agents can identify associates of persons of interest as well as find postings, tweets, photos, or other evidence.⁵ From an

¹ [What social media told us in the time of COVID-19: a scoping review - The Lancet Digital Health.](#)

² Urs E. Gattiker, in [Social Media Audits](#), 2014.

³ [reliefweb.int.](#)

⁴ By David MUGUSHA, social media forensic investigative process for law enforcement agencies, March, 2019.

⁵ Ibid.

intelligence standpoint, this can be extremely successful in monitoring and disrupting organized crime networks such as drug trafficking and prostitution, undermine one culture, race, ethnic origin, in Ethiopia, which frequently utilize social media platforms to promote their illicit activity.⁶ Law enforcement's use of social media in criminal investigations should be an essential tool in avoiding crime and uncovering evidence and individuals linked to illegal conduct.⁷

Crime investigation in social media is not easy as the investigation in the crime scene area. It is controlled and owned by the private actors, private company. The company of the social media are very trustful for their customers and ensure their customers the right to freedom of expression in the platform. However, investigating social media is a complex process which involves the privacy issues for accessing the users, suspects and victims' information on social media. To conduct crime investigation the law enforcement organs should get the company and get the evidence from the data base. To get the evidence there may be factors that permits the organs to access the data and the explanation of the issue. The factors might be the location or, head quarter of the company, the economic leverage level of the country, the domestic legislation of the country and the privacy issue of the users. The real and the fake account creators are common in the countries like Ethiopia in Africa. These creators disseminate disinformation or hate speech on the social media platforms once and erases the post. For example, the account named, 'excellency center' in Southern Ethiopia Region, disseminates many disinformation and hate speech on the nations, ethnic groups, and public officials, the false appointment and removal of political leaders. Even though Ethiopia has the recently promulgated law of the disinformation and hate speech,⁸ nobody can get the information and evidence of the media users. Since the country has no the data protection and strong the privacy rights law, it cannot access the data base of the company.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ The LexisNexis Social Media Use in Law Enforcement report, 2014.

⁸ Hate Speech and Disinformation Prevention and Suppression Proclamation No.1185 /2020.

3. FREEDOM OF EXPRESSION ON SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORM

Freedom of expression is a natural right of human being in the globe. It may be individual right as personal fulfilment and to exercise its right in society, for democracy.⁹ ICCPR, Article 19, sub-1 Everyone shall have the right to hold opinions without interference. Sub-2, Everyone shall have the right to freedom of expression; this right shall include freedom to seek, receive and impart information and ideas of all kinds, regardless of frontiers, either orally, in writing or in print, in the form of art, or through any other media of his choice.¹⁰ Even the European Convention on human rights interprets widely, Article 10(1) is applicable not only to information or ideas that are favourably received or regarded as inoffensive or as a matter of indifference, but also to those that offend, shock or disturb the State or any sector of the population.¹¹ Such are the demands of that pluralism, tolerance and broadmindedness without which there is no democratic society. The exercise of the rights provided for in paragraph 2 of this article carries with it special duties and responsibilities. It may therefore be subject to certain restrictions, but these shall only be such as are provided by law and are necessary: (1) For respect of the rights or reputations of others; (2) For the protection of national security or of public order, or of public health or morals.”

Human rights instruments in the world provides any persons to express any idea or opinions or speech freely unless prohibited in the exception cases, that is prescribed by law, necessary action and for proportional actions. For instance, ICCPR, Art. 20(1):¹² Any propaganda for war shall be prohibited by law, ICCPR, Art. 20(2)¹³: Any advocacy of national, racial or religious hatred that constitutes incitement to discrimination, hostility or violence shall be prohibited by law. Laws that penalize the expression of opinions about historical facts are incompatible with the obligations that the Covenant imposes on States parties in relation to the respect for freedom of opinion and expression. The Covenant does not permit general prohibition of expressions of an erroneous opinion or an incorrect interpretation of past events. Principle 5, 2019 Declaration of Principles of Freedom of Expression and Access to Information in Africa provides the exercise

⁹ ICCPR, Article 19 (1)

¹⁰ Ibid, Art.2

¹¹ European Convention on Human Rights, Article 10(1).

¹² ICCPR, Art. 20(1).

¹³ Ibid, article 20(2).

of the rights to freedom of expression and access to information shall be protected from interference both online and offline, and States shall interpret and implement the protection of these rights in this Declaration and other relevant international standards accordingly.¹⁴

Types of speech and expression that States may desire to limit or regulate. These are political/critical of the government, commercial speech/advertising, hate speech (e.g. policing comments online; ECtHR *Delfi v. Estonia*), speech inciting to violence or discrimination (e.g. Facebook/Rohingya), Offensive and blasphemous speech (e.g. pornography; cartoons of Prophet Muhammed), Untruthful speech (e.g. defamation, “fake news”), truthful speech intrusive of privacy (including, e.g. sextortion). Interaction between government and private actors are needed when there is crime and in case if happened, facilitating crime investigation to make the criminal liable. So, regulation of social media platforms by the state and by the platforms themselves very important to bring the social media criminals to justice.

4. SOCIO ECONOMIC OPPORTUNITY AND CHALLENGES OF SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media is becoming an important tool for social and economical and professional growth. Social media are widely used with bulky aims, leveling from attempts to reach wider audiences, to attract different people, to offer alternative means for interaction with citizens and/or other stakeholders. There are many possibilities and there is big resource use social media as one of the lubricants for providing good governance of the country for democracy process, citizens participation, good business, good marketing, good diplomacy and good manufacturing system. The most radical and advanced technologies of the recent time is the emergence of social media as major tools of commercial, entertainment, political and social affairs, educational, criminal investigation tool. Social media fields are a good stage of a communication channels that facilitate problem solving in creative business and commercial purposes, educational sectors, other governmental and or non-governmental organizations. The power of social media paved the way to play important role in terms of economic development and expansion. It also has many implicit values that will be revealed in the long development of the world economy. The current economic performance in the globe is the result of development of social media. Sophisticating market performance by boosting the promotion and advertisement of the market

¹⁴ Declaration of Principles on Freedom of Expression and Access to Information in Africa 2019.

products. It grows the trustfulness of the customer to the product, the transparency of every activity. Social media opens up channels for businesses to efficiently connect with customers, suppliers and investors that it must be positive for business outcomes. For example, social media enables entrepreneurs to create and maintain weak ties and bridging social capital.¹⁵ While Facebook is generally regarded as being useful for maintaining strong ties such as close friends or kin, Twitter enables entrepreneurs to expand and use their weak ties such as acquaintances.¹⁶

Growth in technology and the internet have greatly influenced the way things are done virtually in all fields of human activities. The effect of social media on human capacity development has gone more than the exchange of information, the social media have become powerful communicative forces in the economic, political, religious and educational interest of the society. Social media facilitates the social and economic activities in the society. Social interactions are very well and important to ensure other interactions fruitful. Social connection is among the most significant benefits of social media. It can connect huge number of users at any time and everywhere in the world. Information, promotions, advertisements or news or innovations could be migrated globally through social media and its network, making the life flexible or people to interact with one another easily. It results the world to one small village and made the relationship of the world people too simple. In some cases, privacy difficulties create a severe degradation in the reputation of numerous prominent social media activities, resulting in a damaging effect on the performing activity. The privacy rules of social media firms, such as Facebook and Twitter, often regulate how businesses utilize user data and how third parties act on the platform concerning personal data. These regulations are commonly known as privacy policies. Users using social media platforms provided by third parties must ensure that their information do not promote activity that potentially violates the privacy regulations of the social media firm. Facebook may result in psychological suppression and wastes time, spending a lot of time on social media sites and then beginning to show symptoms of depression through social segregating from their environment, friends, peer groups, and their families, with some resorting to using bad sites and blogs, which may promote addiction or sexual activities and/or destructing brain and that leads self-aggressive behaviours. Social media flied may yield to the separation

¹⁵ Robert Ackland, Australian National University, Kyosuke Tanaka, Australian National University, Development Impact of social media, Background paper prepared for the World Development Report 2016: Internet for Development, 25 July, 2015.

¹⁶ Ibid.

and affecting of family relations. Easily disseminates of crimes, that is hate speech, defamation, pornography or bad sexual activities on the platform.

5. GLOBALIZATION AND SOCIAL MEDIA CRIMES IN THE DIFFERENT JURISDICTIONS

Since the globalization, the world is in one village and get any information in one time. The technology and internet made the world one local area or we can say one house. Benefiting the connection is possible as much as the user's capacity goes. We can get the information of the incident occurred in USA one states as equal as the inhabitants there due to technology and internet through social media. You can conduct any business, involve in the market, be member of any trade organization, you can be online employee of any trade organizations, for example, can be employee of Alibaba, amazon, etc. Promote and advertise the products and service of the company through social media platform. The technology and internet emergence has provided individuals with a new platform and has developed to the performance that it is now a part of everyday life. In our current universe, there has been the development of a quick medium for the global exchange of ideas. Social media has a prominent impact on people's daily activities, whether for good or bad. In the modern time people can't imagine its lives without social media, therefore it's no surprise that criminal activity involving social media has also become a norm. Due to the booming of social media coverage, crime has been able to grow in high speed through online. Individuals, group of people, government agencies, non-governmental organizations and commercial companies, etc., have all gather the benefits of social media coverages. However, the technology has abundant benefits, it also has many disadvantages, sophisticated way of crimes begins to happen online. The security of people, privacy right and dignity may have been threatened by social media, which has led to a rise in cyber violence and a difficult situation on a global scale. Two things should be solved here, one is using the good parts of the social media wisely and properly, the other thing is managing the crimes of social media as well by different ways, developing the laws which can protect the modern social media crimes. World gives more attentions to prevent the social media crimes by amending the existing laws, or promulgating the new laws as the globalizations made the world narrow and one house, family. EU promulgated new laws, which can protect the media crimes and laid the procedures of investigating media

crimes and to make liable the media criminals. Concerning the offline crimes EU realized the best crime protection mechanism in the Treaty of Amsterdam which was came into force and recognized and achieved an area of Security, freedom and Justice. In 1999 EU get consensus at the Tampere Conclusions, proclaimed the first crime preventive methods along with the Union's basic responsibility to protect its citizens.¹⁷ After a mean later the European Crime Prevention Network was established, in 2001¹⁸ and it was then provided that crime prevention should be based on more technic and knowledge, tactic and strategic enough plan and carried out through cooperation and an increased inter-state exchange of ideas and information. The Member States have a great cooperative obligation and the work should be carried out by a multidimensional approach specialising on certain selected serious cases. Successful and fruitful practices need to be exchanged within the network and evaluation of the preventive work must be done. The European directive on Combating Terrorism and Proposed Regulation preventing the dissemination of terrorist content.¹⁹ It gives the mandate to the member states to ensure that the making available of a message to the public with an intentional incitement to commit a terrorist offence is punishable as a criminal offence.²⁰ It obligates the states to take the necessary measures to ensure the quick removal of the online content constituting a public instigation to commit a terrorist offence.²¹ EU promulgated the directive which combats the sexual exploitation of children and child pornography.²² The directive rules member states legislation to criminalise the most serious forms of sexual abuse towards children.²³ The regulation highly criminalizes and lay the high punishment on the websites transmitting or disseminating child pornography.²⁴ And also EU established serious and strong laws to combat any crimes on the social media and on the technology and internet and any illegal activities online.²⁵ South Africa, in Africa has timely enacted the law to manage the cybercrimes via internet on computer, which

¹⁷ Tampere European Council, Presidency Conclusions, 15 AND 16 OCTOBER 1999.

¹⁸ The European Crime Prevention Network (EUCPN) was set up on 28 May 2001 and then re-established on 30 November 2009 by a [Council Decision](#).

¹⁹ Directive (EU) 2017/541 on Combating Terrorism and Proposed Regulation COM (2018) 640 on preventing the dissemination of terrorist content, article 5.

²⁰ Ibid.

²¹ Ibid. Art. 21.

²² The Directive replaces Council Framework Decision 2004/68/JHA, Directive 2011/93/EU on combating the sexual abuse and sexual exploitation of children and child pornography.

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ Ibid, Article 25.

²⁵ The European Commission Recommendation (EU) 2018/334 on measures to effectively tackle illegal content online (Section 2.6.2.).

includes the apparatus of smart phones and tablets.²⁶ These crimes targets on the confidentiality, data on the computer, integrity of the person, may be defamation, insult and other humiliating activities which may incur psychological and material costs.²⁷ South Africa enacted electronic communications and transaction acts,²⁸ criminalized the child pornography.²⁹ South Africa is somewhat good when we see with other African countries on the crime combating strategy and laws on the online crimes. Tanzania adopted its first information communication technology policy to manage crimes in cyber space.³⁰ Following the policy, the country promulgated cybercrime act, in 2015. After the development of laws in the sector, there are laws managing online crimes, like social media crimes which is good in Africa relatively even though, unlike south Africa which is advanced. Ethiopia drafted its first national information and communication technology policy in 2016. By considering, to play a stronger role in Ethiopia's aspiration to become a middle-income economy and transforming the country into a leading tech hub in the region. Secondly, the policy provides a pro-active strategy and regulatory framework that is not only in sync with contemporary technological realities and dynamics, but also seeks to guide the orderly development of the ICT sector in such a way as to ensure maximum developmental impact for the benefit of all Ethiopians. Fourthly, this policy takes cognizance of the tremendous impact of globalization and rapid technological change since the first policy was implemented. These developments have invariably affected the traditional approach to the management of public affairs and delivery of services, which increasingly informs the need for a more pro-active policy and response from the government.³¹ Following this policy the country could not promulgate the independent laws to manage highly developing social media crimes.

²⁶ Department of Justice and Constitutional Development: Republic of South Africa Cybercrimes and Cybersecurity Bill, 2017.

²⁷ Ibid.

²⁸ The Electronic Communications and Transactions Act (ECT Act), 2002.

²⁹ Films and Publications Act 65 of 1996, South Africa.

³⁰ The National ICT Policy 2003 (NICTP 2003) is revised by of the NICTP 2016 and 2019.

³¹ FDRE National Information and Communication Technology Policy, 2016, preamble.

6. PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION VIS-A-VIS PRIVACY LAWS IN THE DIGITAL PERIOD

In this topic we can assess the data protection law as a different era, how to data protection law can be employed to safeguard private online and to go on the EU General Data protection regulation which is advanced in this time. The personal data protection is one of the fundamental rights of human being in this era. Europe states developed domestic data protection laws in many years back. In the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, there are different provisions of data protection and privacy laws. Article, 7 says,³² everyone has the right to respect for his or her private and family life, home and communications. Article 8(1) provides Everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her.³³ In sub-2 it tells that the privacy right can be limited by the legal provision. Provides that, ... “such data must be processed fairly for specified purposes and on the basis of the consent of the person concerned or some other legitimate basis laid down by law. Everyone has the right of access to data which has been collected concerning him or her, and the right to have it rectified.”³⁴

Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union has the provision of personal data protection. It states, everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning them. In the international human rights law, the privacy issue and the personal data protections are intermingled. Universal Declaration of Human Rights, article 12, and ICCPR, Article 17 states similar terms and similar rights, both states, UDHR, Article 12, “No one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to attacks upon his honour and reputation. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks” ICCPR, Article 17, “1. No one shall be subjected to arbitrary or unlawful interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to unlawful attacks upon his honor and reputation. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks”.

³² Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, Article 7.

³³ Ibid, Article 8(1).

³⁴ Ibid, Article 8(2).

Article 8 of European convention on human rights, states identical phrases as provided below,

1. Everyone has the right to respect for his private and family life, his home and correspondence.
2. There shall be no interference by a public authority with the exercise of this right except such as is in accordance with the law and is necessary in a democratic society in the interests of national security, public safety or the economic well-being of the country, for the prevention of disorder or crime, for the protection of health or morals, or for the protection of the rights and freedoms of others". In these above two huge and very basic important international human rights laws and the giant European human rights instrument there are no separated personal data protection provisions but they are covered by these privacy right provisions.

However, recently European Union promulgated the independent law of general personal data protection law in 2016. Which ensures the rights of natural persons to process, access, use and free movement of any data in electronic and online instruments without interference of any persons or authorities.³⁵ The South African government enacted protection of personal information act, 2013. This act protects its citizens from abusing the data in any online or offline media. If social media crime has been committed, the law enforcement organs can access the data source in order to make the suspect criminal according to the personal information act. Tanzania has no vivid personal data protection laws like other countries in continent even though relatively good when we compare with Ethiopia. Even though there are data protection laws, there are government practice to extract data from the private actors like Facebook, twitters. It is obvious that government agencies extract social networking websites for evidence. Even without having to seek a warrant from the court or issue a permission. New York Police Department has

³⁵ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the Protection of Natural Persons with regard to the Processing of Personal Data and on the Free Movement of Such Data, and Repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).

a social media unit that mines Facebook, Twitter, and other social media sites for evidence of crimes and potential criminal activity.³⁶

Most of government authorities are active participants who contribute content and solicit information through social media. Given the amount of information publicly available and the avenues that the government has to seek out such information, usually the government does not need a search warrant, a permission, or court order to obtain social media evidence, American States.³⁷ In addition to searching for publicly available evidence, government agents are allowed to go further than defense counsel in pursuing social media evidence for a criminal proceeding. To bypass the need for a search warrant, government agents may pierce the privacy settings of a person's social media account by creating fake online identities or by securing cooperating witnesses to grant them access to information in the American States.³⁸ There are also Federal law which provides that in some circumstances, the government may compel social media companies to produce social media evidence without a warrant. America has the Stored Communications Act (SCA) governs the ability of governmental entities to compel service providers, such as Twitter and Facebook, to produce content (e.g., posts and tweets) and non-content customer records (e.g., name and address) in certain circumstances. With regard to the compelled disclosure of communication content, the Stored Communication Act provides different levels of statutory privacy protection depending on how long the content has been in electronic storage.³⁹ Which is similar with the general data protection regulations of European Union laws. These are strong laws which can manage crime investigation on the crimes of social media.

³⁶ U.S. Dept. Of Homeland Sec., Privacy Impact Assessment For The Office Of Operations Coordination And Planning: Publicly Available Social Media Monitoring And Situational Awareness Initiative 3 (2010), available at http://www.dhs.gov/xlibrary/assets/privacy/privacy_pia_ops_publiclyavailablesocialmedia.pdf (noting that the National Operations Center will use publicly available search engines and content aggregators to monitor activities on social media sites); see also Role of Social Media in Law Enforcement Significant and Growing, LEXISNEXIS (July 18, 2012), <http://www.lexisnexis.com/media/press-release.aspx?id=1342623085481181> (stating that, according to the results of a comprehensive survey, over eighty percent of local and federal agencies use social media during investigations).

³⁷ Study Shows 66% of Government Organizations Have Adopted Social Networking, Collaboration Tools, SABA (Jan. 14, 2010), <http://www.saba.com/company/press-releases/2010/saba-and-hci-publish-study-of-social-networking-in-government/>.

³⁸ United States v. Meregildo, No. 11 Cr. 576(WHP), 2012 WL 3264501, at *2 (S.D.N.Y. Aug. 10, 2012).

³⁹ United States v. Warshak, 631 F.3d 266, 282 (6th Cir. 2010) (citing 18 U.S.C. §§ 2701-2711); see also Crispin v. Christian Audigier, Inc., 717 F. Supp. 2d 965, 977 (C.D. Cal. 2010) (applying the SCA to subpoenas issued to Facebook and MySpace while recognizing that no courts "have addressed whether social-networking sites fall within the ambit of the statute").

7. PUBLIC INTEREST VERSUS PRIVATE INTEREST IN THE INVESTIGATION OF SOCIAL MEDIA CRIMES.

The acceptance of a public interest presupposes that we accept that society is a single whole which shares common ethical values. The public interest was seen as a crucial element to explain the purpose and role of public planning. The concept of the public interest arises from two major lines of liberal philosophical and historical thought, utilitarianism and contractarianism. As well as these lines of thinking, we must also refer to Habermas's theory of communicative action, which introduced a new perspective in the concept of public interest. These philosophies have in common the fact that they consider the public interest to be a means to the achievement of a fairer society, although their different notions of fairness are another question.⁴⁰ Utilitarianism proposes that the public interest is the increase of social wellbeing. The utilitarian method does not, however, address the way in which the increased social wellbeing is distributed between individuals and social groups. Utilitarianism uses an aggregatory principle and the question of fairness is seen simply as a matter of the maximization of collective utility. Such aggregation, though, can mask deep and unacceptable inequalities which, ethically, must be rejected. The contractarian approach represents a change of tack. Attention centres on the least favored members of society. Drawing from these theories and concepts, the society bases many demands from the government as whole than the individuals. Important infrastructures, like road, water, buildings, telecommunications, electricity, internet and others base society rather than individual which can be lived as its personal interests, lifestyle, choice and social base.

Individualism bases on the interest, life style, social ties, choices. Individual has its own interests based on culture, economic capacity and political view. The life style is depended on the fashion, attitude, behavior and educational, economical and also social and cultural bases. Individuals' social connection and choice are depending its personal willing. Protecting the public at large secures the society at large that is the collection of individuals. It is fact that protecting all individual interest ensures and attains the fulfilling of the interest of the society at whole. But fulfilling all individuals interest as a whole at equal manner is very difficult but seeing the society at which individuals gain its interest as its capacity goes to get interests is very preferable in the world concepts. Among the society individual does a certain crime online or offline. One

⁴⁰ Manuel Benabent F. De Córdoba Arenal Grupo Consultor S.L., Public Interest in Political Philosophy. A Necessary Ethical and Regulatory Concept for Territorial Planning, 2010.

individual commits the crime that results the bad for the society all. Not every society do crime at one time. However, an individual can do. When caring for one individual the society may face dangerous situation by the crime. For the interest of the society the government extract the personal data and may violate privacy rights of the individuals. But it should be proportional, necessary and it should be prescribed by the law of domestic legislations.

8. EU PRACTICES HANDLING CRIME INVESTIGATION OF SOCIAL MEDIA PRIVACY

EU has well adequate and sufficient laws which regulates the processing by an individual, a company or an organization of personal data relating to individuals in the its jurisdiction in the history. The EU general data protection regulation (GDPR) is the strongest privacy and security law in the world. Before, that the data protection directive of 1995 was also active and better in the world standard. Which was replaced and updated by the new strong and modernized regulation that is General data protection regulation 2016. The right to the protection of personal data is not an absolute right; it must be considered in relation to its function in society and be balanced against other fundamental rights, in accordance with the principle of proportionality. This Regulation respects all fundamental rights and observes the freedoms and principles recognized in the Charter as enshrined in the Treaties, in particular the respect for private and family life, home and communications, the protection of personal data, freedom of thought, conscience and religion, freedom of expression and information, freedom to conduct a business, the right to an effective remedy and to a fair trial, and cultural, religious and linguistic diversity.⁴¹ Member States may restrict by way of a legislative act the scope of DP obligations and rights of the data subject if the restriction is required to safeguard, national security, defense, public security, for prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, other important objectives of general public interests (economic or financial).⁴² The restriction must respect “the essence of the fundamental rights and freedoms and is a necessary and proportionate measure in a democratic society.”⁴³ The scope of the regulation extends to non-EU member countries that is the wideness of the regulation.⁴⁴ It is what we call the smart law of the general data protection. The definition of personal data in the

⁴¹ General Data protection regulation 2016, Article 4.

⁴² GDPR, Art. 23(1)

⁴³ Ibid.

⁴⁴ Ibid., Article, 24.

regulation is wide and exhaustively mentioned every activity of online or offline. It states: “Personal data’ means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.” It is well organized and well sufficient law of the data protection in the world. It can be great example for the remaining parts of the globe. On the basis of this law any law enforcement organ can conduct the crime investigation by accessing the data of any individuals by referring the law and ordering the private actor companies by the laws. Since the privacy issue is not absolute if the suspect is suspected by the crime on the social media, the investigating authority can access his/her data base. However, in the Africa there has been an inclusive debate about how cultures outside the Western world handle the idea of privacy, both in their everyday lives and in their laws. In the context of African countries, the right to privacy and personal data protection haven’t been well defined, explained, or protected in comparison with EU countries. To implement the regulation the EU countries, have many economic leverages to the social media company like Facebook, Twitters to create good influence. Headquarter of the company is located in US and EU, which helps to order the company in its jurisdiction that lubricates the situation more to access the social media company. The economic leverage to the company may be the bargaining means to access the data of the media suspects of the crime. The headquarter more useful to materialize the order of the court to take the information or data from the base. More than these the basic points raised above, The EU has modernized and strong privacy law that ensures that social media platforms and other data controllers provide access to data upon request by law enforcement agencies and courts. The EU besides having the most advanced data protection law in the world has a parallel legislation dealing with data protection and law enforcement name the Law Enforcement Directive. These the impact of the lack of the economic and institutional leverage of African countries on social media platforms has not been researched. African countries like South Africa and Tanzania have a little bit good data protection law with privacy right laws. Privacy is a valuable aspect of personality. Data or information protection forms an element of safeguarding a person’s right to privacy. It provides for the legal protection of a person in instances where his or her personal information is being collected, stored, used or

communicated by another person or institution. South Africa has the right to privacy in common law and in the Constitution.⁴⁵ The recognition and protection of the right to privacy as a fundamental human right in the Constitution⁴⁶ provides an indication of its importance.⁴⁷ Tanzania has also the recent the personal data protection which is promulgated in 2022. It protects both the privacy and personal data security rights. Its constitution also provided the rights of privacy and personal data protections.⁴⁸ To implement these laws in according with economic and institutional influence, it is late and back. The economic leverage from the country to the social media company is very low in comparison with other US., EU and some African countries like Nigeria, Ghana. So, it is more or less difficult to access the data base of social media company to conduct the social media crime investigation. There is no headquarter of the giant social media company in the country, that is another problem to access the evidence and data from the company to perform the crime investigation of social media. Unlike EU, South Africa, Tanzania, Ethiopia is the least in using privacy rights, personal data protection laws. There is provision in the constitution of privacy right, which has paper value and has no practical value. The provision consists the privacy and data protection rights both at one article. It is wide states, Article 26(1) ... everyone has the right to privacy, which includes, searches of his home, person or property, or the seizure of any property under /his personal possession,⁴⁹ sub-2, provides, inviolability of his notes and correspondence including postal letters, and communications made by means of telephone, telecommunications and electronic devices.⁵⁰ It is restricted for the purposes shall be the safeguarding of national security or public peace, the prevention of crimes or the protection of health, public morality or the rights and freedoms of others.⁵¹ There is no other special law which manages personal data and privacy rights as law to access the social media company. Less economic leverage and lack of office of the institution the Ethiopian Country can not access the social media data base, for this reason the country can not entertain the crime investigation on media platform. For these reasons the social media misinformation and hate speech shakes, disturbs makes chaos in the country. It incurs huge

⁴⁵ The South African Law Reform Commission was established by the South African Law Commission Act, 1973 (Act 19 of 1973)

⁴⁶ South African Constitution, 1996, section 14.

⁴⁷ Ibid.

⁴⁸ The Republic of Tanzania Constitution, 1977, Article 16.

⁴⁹ Supra note 1, Article 26(1)

⁵⁰ Ibid, sub-2.

⁵¹ Ibid, subu-2

financial costs to the government to rebalance the dissemination of the disinformation and hate news. The EU general data protection regulation is very sophisticate and exhaustive law that can be extended to non-member countries in the jurisdictions and out of the jurisdiction to the citizens of the EU member countries.

9. CONCLUDING REMARKS!

To conduct the crime investigation of giant social media crimes on the platform, there should three basic requirements needed and fulfilled at EU standard. There should be very modernized, sophisticate, well adequate and sufficient laws of general data protection law or personal data protection and strong privacy rights domestic legislations. The second one is the high economic leverage to social media company to deal great bargaining to access the data base of the social media company to start and pursue the crime investigation of social media crimes. Without economy you cannot fully think of and implement the domestic legislation as it is. There should be the office of the institution or the headquarter of the company to enforce the court orders as quickly as possible and manage getting data base access in its jurisdictions. However, the economy the solid base to bargain with and to order the private actors, social media company to get data from the data base of the company to investigate the crime on the platform. In the current world there are a few countries which can control the data controllers to manage the data base in according with the domestic laws. US. And EU are very able to implement their laws timely since they fulfil the above issues. Other African countries should promulgate strong laws to access the data base, try to increase the economic leverage to the social media company without blocking the media platform for the freedom of expression and exercise of basic human rights on the platform. Making the good relationship with the company to open the branch of the office or the institution in the country to get data from the company to prevent the social media crime by investigating the crime ,as result to make the criminal liable, thereby make the country free from the social media disinformation and hate speech spreading which make the country instable and ground for the social media mess and chaos that costs the government highly other than normal and planned.